

RADIANT CREATOR

Workshop

“UC Week”

2-3 June, 2025, Budapest

Hosted by ESSRG

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Executive Summary

The primary objective of the event was to raise awareness and promote the importance of forgotten and underutilised crops (UCs) through a series of engaging activities. The event aimed to foster collaboration and networking among researchers and practitioners involved in the cultivation, research, and commercialisation of these crops. By highlighting their diverse values and benefits, the event sought to promote sustainable agricultural practices. Building on the diverse portfolio of food researchers in ESSRG, we assessed potential networks, showcased best practices, research findings, and success stories that can serve as a resource for business, public sector or civic stakeholders interested in UCs. We included in the agenda workshops on UCs, panel discussions featuring experts and success stories from the field, policy convergence discussions with the sister project DIVINFOOD, networking opportunities for participants to share insights and establish connections, and an exhibition showcasing various UCs and their potential arts-based meaning-making. For promotion, we used social media and partnerships with related organisations, such as the EU Green Week, which listed this event among its partner events. The event was designed to meet participants' needs, foster interactions, and collect feedback to gauge interest and engagement levels. As a primary outcome, the workshop facilitated new connections and collaborations among researchers, farmers, and stakeholders, which will lead to additional projects related to UCs. The joint event with the sister project DIVINFOOD also laid the groundwork for continued exploration and promotion of UCs, pointing out the importance of more vibrant dialogues and joint actions focused on underutilised crops. The outcome enabled participants to collaboratively leverage these resources for broader impacts on food systems and agrobiodiversity.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and objectives

The aim of the workshop was to discuss the different aspects of UCs within the food system and to provide opportunities to foster collaboration among different actors; researchers and practitioners involved in the cultivation, research, and commercialisation of UCs. During the workshop, a variety of activities was organized to engage participants in discussions, hands-on activities, creative and embodied experiences.

Building on the resources and network of ESSRG, the event showcased best practices, research findings, and success stories through ESSRG's diverse portfolio of food research. Within ESSRG, a group of dedicated researchers is working on various projects related to the food system. The variety of food related research projects helps to uncover the different aspects of the food system, from breeding to consumption and create synergies. Among these researches, agrobiodiversity, and the use of UCs are key to support resilient agri-food systems.

As one of the main tasks of ESSRG is to explore how policies can support transition toward a sustainable food system, including the RADIANT project, discussions were organized around this topic. During discussions and presentations, we aimed to shed light on links between policies and agrobiodiversity, for example change in seed laws and its consequences on accessing and conserving seeds of UCs, and how it affects stakeholders.

The event included a joint roundtable discussion co-organized with the DIVINFOOD project to foster collaboration between the sister projects and among researchers and practitioners. The joint event aimed at converging the policy work carried out by the two projects and ensuring the continuity of discussion around how policies can support the use of UCs.

In addition to discussions and presentations, the event aimed at inviting participants to discover creative and art-based methods to address UC-related topics via the 'HOPEN' workshop and the exhibition entitled 'Traces of Life'. During a field visit, one of the AURORA farms of the RADIANT project was showcased to allow participants to gain better understanding on small-scale farming dedicated to agrobiodiversity, and to initiate discussion among researchers, farmers, business and civil society actors.

1.2 Workshop framework and participants

The creator workshop in Budapest took place between 2-3 June. The workshop was followed by the DIVERSCROPS Science & Policy Training School between 4-5 June, as a side event.

During the two days of the creator workshop, altogether 17 people participated of which 13 belonged to academia, one participant to both academia and civil sector, one participant to the processing sector and two participants represented growers. Participants came from Hungary (10), Portugal (2), Scotland (2), Germany (1) and Greece (2).

The program overview is included in Annex I. All programs were held in English.

Day 1

ESSRG's Food Projects: explore and network

Participants were invited to discover ESSRG's food projects, and they had the opportunity for networking among ESSRG members and RADIANT partners. Via short presentations, 10 projects were showcased, which either directly (for example, LegumES, Cousin) or indirectly (FoodClic, Plan'Eat, WiseFood, Mosaic, EcoNutri, Coevolvers) were related to the RADIANT project. The presentations and the following discussion aimed at uncovering how ESSRG team seeks to shape the food system and have an impact on food policies, how they work with local authorities and stakeholders.

HOPEN Workshop

In the second part of day one, participants were invited to immerse themselves in the 'HOPEN process', an internal exploration to reflect on the professional journey of participants. The workshop was developed in the framework of the Trigger project, and it was facilitated by Diana Szakál and Zsófia Kollányi (ESSRG).

Visit to the exhibition "Traces of Life"

At the end of day one, participants were invited to visit the exhibition entitled "Traces of Life" at the CEU Open Gallery, taking part in the OFF Biennale Budapest 2025. OFF Biennale Budapest is an independent, grassroots contemporary art event in Budapest, organized at various places citywide. OFF Biennale Budapest aims to initiate public discussion about neglected social, political, and environmental issues via contemporary art.

The exhibition “Traces of Life” reflected on the interdependence of human and non-human life, including a seed library. More information can be found here: <https://offbiennale2025.hu/en/kiallitas/traces-of-life/>.

The first day of the event was concluded by a dinner at the charming rooftop of the Central European University, offered by ESSRG.

Day 2

Visit of Szezon Kert

The first part of day two of the creator workshop was dedicated to the visit of the RADIANT Aurora Farms, Szezon Kert, located at Páty. Katalin Réthy, owner of Szezon Kert, presented her vegetable garden and her experience as a small-scale farmer dedicated to agrobiodiversity and to experiment with UCs. For more details see section 3.1

Katalin Réthy, being the president of Magház Association, a Hungarian community seed bank, and her garden being an important place for seed saving, discussions were organized about seeds, seeds saving and seed policies. UC production starts with the seeds. However, access to seeds of less common species is limited. How can farmers access UC seeds? How does a community seed bank work? Participants were invited to learn about seed saving networks, hear about the experiences of the Hungarian Seed Saving Network (Magház), and to discuss seed policies that are currently under discussion in the European Union. Discussion on seeds also included a workshop about current seeds laws and the upcoming seed legislation, presented by Borbála Lipka (ESSRG, Magház).

As a taste of agrobiodiversity and UCs, the morning was concluded by a delicious lunch made of black chickpeas produced at Szezon Kert.

Figure 1. Black chickpeas produced at Szezon Kert

Policy convergence roundtable (RADIANT – LegumES – Divinfood)

As a last program, the participants of the creator workshop joined the 'Policy convergence roundtable', co-organized by the RADIANT, LegumES and Divinfood project embedded in the annual meeting of the Divinfood project. During the roundtable discussion, invited speakers explored how policies can support UCs. The roundtable converged around creating momentum at the local and European levels for cultivated biodiversity, given that food and agriculture policies at various institutional and sectoral scales may play a pivotal role in stimulating the incorporation of agrobiodiversity in the food system.

2. Presentations and Sessions

2.1 ESSRG Food Projects Presentations

Following welcoming words by Bálint Balázs, ESSRG colleagues showcased a selection of projects and good practices in food system research. Presentations covered projects directly related to RADIANT, such as the LegumES project focusing on ecosystem services provided by legumes, or the Cousin project promoting crop wild relatives. Other projects, such as the FoodClic, are more related to local food systems, or in the case of the Plan'Eat and the WiseFood project, to consumption. In other food projects, such as the Mosaic, Coevolvers or the EcoNutri, different actors are involved to promote agrobiodiversity in land use, mental care or in sustainable nutrient management.

Figure 2. ESSRG Food Projects presentation

In most of the tasks ESSRG leads or is involved in, stakeholder engagement, development and coordination of Living Labs and interaction with a wide range of actors of the food system play an important role. Socio-economic assessment, including policy analysis, development of food policies, recommendations and policy briefs represent a significant part in ESSRG's food system research.

The presentation can be found at:

<https://prezi.com/view/dX9hkZkr1fM3krDntLQJ/>

Presentation included the following speakers:

Orsolya Lazányi: **RADIANT - Realizing Dynamic Value Chains for Underutilised Crops**

ESSRG leads WP5 on Enabling Transformations: Sociocultural Evaluations and Policy Incentives including:

- analysing the implication of current policy and governance of agrifood systems on the use of UCs
 - formulating policy and governance recommendations (policy briefs) for mainstreaming UCs in current agrifood systems, and
 - producing a Policy Incentive Catalogue.
-

Ágnes Neulinger: **LegumES - Valorising and balancing the ecosystem service benefits offered by legumes, and legume-based cropped systems**

ESSRG tasks cover

- leading the expert dialogue on policy solutions for legume-based production and,
 - contributing to the identification of policy instruments for legumes and recommendations for the development of a legume-based food and farming system.
-

Kata Fodor: **COUSIN - Crop Wild Relatives Utilisation and Conservation for Sustainable Agriculture**

ESSRG's tasks cover

- co-creating a favourable context for CWRs by engaging diverse stakeholders,
 - identifying strategic guidelines for practitioners, and
 - providing policy recommendations for decision-makers.
-

Éva Bánsági: **FOODCLIC - integrated urban FOOD policies – developing sustainability Co-benefits, spatial Linkages, social Inclusion and sectoral Connections to transform food systems in city-regions**

ESSRG tasks cover

- mapping local stakeholders to identify networks and actors engaged with city-regional food systems
- mapping urban food environments and food systems (system understanding, visioning)
- supporting the development and implementation of integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks
- monitoring and assessing real-life interventions and stimulating reflexions.

Diana Szakál: **PLAN'EAT - Food systems transformation towards healthy and sustainable dietary behaviour**

ESSRG coordinates the work of 9 Living Labs across Europe, as well as leads the Budapest LL that collaborates with single-parent families, one of Hungary's most vulnerable groups, as they are at risk of poverty or exclusion, and supports their dietary transition.

Bálint Balázs: **WiseFood - Where Data Feeds Decisions Aiming to develop smart digital applications that empower citizens to adopt healthier and eco-friendly food choices**

ESSRG is evaluating innovative digital applications that enable citizens to make healthier and more eco-friendly food choices.

Boldizsár Megyesi: **MOSAIC - Innovative and Effective Policies For Sustainable Land Use Change**

ESSRG leads the Hungarian Policy Lab, interregional learning and capacity building for project partners and local stakeholders, while supporting the qualitative case study research on drivers behind land use change.

Bálint Balázs: **EcoNutri - Innovative concepts and technologies for ECOlogically sustainable NUTRIent management in agriculture aiming to prevent, mitigate and eliminate pollution in soils, water and air**

ESSRG leads the socioeconomic assessment and contributes to policy mapping, co-design, and the development of recommendations.

Orsolya Lazányi: **COEVOLVERS - Coevolutionary approach to unlock the transformative potential of nature-based solutions for more inclusive and resilient communities**

ESSRG tasks cover

- participating in the Healing Garden Living Lab to co-design a healing and edible garden in a mental healthcare institute together with the clients, healthcare professionals, and environment and gardening experts, and
 - leading communication WP.
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Bálint Balázs: **Transforming agrifood systems in the Europe and Central Asia region**

The ESSRG task is to explore how to improve the sustainability of urban food systems in three Central-Asian countries (Bosnia-Herzegovina, Armenia, Uzbekistan) via

- Urban food systems analysis
 - Successful initiatives catalogue
 - Regional webinar
-

Diana Szakál: **TRIGGER - Solutions for mItiGatinG climate-induced hEalth thReats**

ESSRG's task is to support CHC Labs, ethical protocol, socio-economic review.

ESSRG sub-projects include

- study on climate anxiety and nature connectedness in youths
- HOPEN – a community mental well-being program for hope and resilience in the polycrisis

2.2 HOPEN workshop

The HOPEN process was born as a response to the increasing pressures that scientists, practitioners, and students on the frontlines working for planetary health and societal transformation face, in the framework of the Trigger project. To facilitate systemic transformations through the integration of action and theory, we must be creative and resourceful while remaining grounded. However, caring for the world in transition starts with caring for our own well-being. We cannot connect to others if we lack connection to our inner selves.

During the 2-hour-long workshop, participants had the opportunity to reflect on their professional journey related to UCs and agrobiodiversity and to resource themselves by "meeting" various parts of their emotional self, going beyond the cognitive. Through facilitated, embodied exercises and individual and group work, participants could engage in a playful and interactive format, taking stock of where they came from, where they find themselves now, and what kind of future they desire to create together. The workshop was facilitated by Diana Szakál and Zsófia Kollányi (ESSRG).

Figure 3. HOPEN workshop

2.3 Policy Convergence Roundtable

The roundtable discussion aimed at converging the different experiences that emerged in the DIVINFOOD and RADIANT projects.

The European project DIVINFOOD (funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme) aims to develop food chains that value under-utilised agrobiodiversity to act against the decline of biodiversity and to meet the growing expectations of consumers for healthy, local products that contribute to sustainable food systems. The project brings together 26 partners from seven countries (Denmark, France, Hungary, Italy, Portugal, Sweden, and Switzerland) and relies on nine living labs to encourage participatory research. The long-term societal challenge is to structure and stabilise territorial networks for collective management of agrobiodiversity, with a view to an economy of the commons that values the ecosystem services provided by the use of underused species and varieties.

This discussion explored how minor crops can galvanise the transition to a much-needed diversity of diets. The roundtable included the following speakers:

The role of public policies and local authorities’ in fostering agrobiodiversity

- Yuna Chiffolleau (Divinfood): Welcome and introduction
- Kinga Lőcsei-Tóth (Budapest Municipality), keynote: Urban Food Policy in Budapest

Framing policies on neglected and underutilized crops (NUCs)

- Bálint Balázs (ESSRG): *Radiant's policy evidence and recommendations*
- Luca Colombo (FIRAB): *The food environment approach to policies in Divinfood*

Territorial experiences on NUCs enabling policies

- Philippe Muscat (Director of Restaurant inter-administratif de Lyon, FR): *The collective catering potential for NUCs*
- Alessandro Cardarelli (President Comunità del Cibo della Maremma, IT): *Local Food Communities in support of agrobiodiversity*
- Kinga Lócsei-Tóth (Deputy Head Climate and Environment Dept., Budapest Municipality, HU): *Biodiversity Atlas and the Municipalities alliance for the environment*

The session concluded with questions from the audience.

Figure 4. Bálint Balázs (ESSRG) presenting RADIANT's policy evidence and recommendations at the Policy Convergence Roundtable during the DIVINFOOD annual meeting

3. Demonstration activity / Field visit

3.1 Visit of Szezon Kert

The second day of the creator workshop was dedicated to visiting Szezon Kert owned by Katalin Réthy, located at Páty. Szezon Kert is a small-scale vegetable garden, one of the AURORA farms of the RADIANT project. At Szezon Kert, Katalin produces a high number of crop varieties, and she is committed to experimenting with new and currently underutilised species. Beyond a personal interest, given the changing climatic conditions, agrobiodiversity, new and forgotten species are key to maintaining an environmentally and economically sustainable food system. Crops are grown using organic and agroecological methods at Szezon Kert; however, the garden does not obtain a certified organic label due to the high administrative requirements, as Katalin explained.

Products of Szezon Kert are currently marketed directly to consumers or at farmers' markets. Katalin has experience cooperating with chefs and restaurants but direct sales for consumers have proved more stable at the moment. Katalin also shared her experience about cooperating with research, as an emerging pillar to sustain an agrobiodiverse vegetable garden.

Figure 5. Katalin Réthy presenting Szezon Kert to the workshop participants

Figure 6. Photos of Szezon Kert during the field visit

Szezon Kert is specialised in seed saving as Katalin is the president of Magház Association, a Hungarian seed saving network. This network consists of small-scale farmers committed to conserving vegetable varieties in situ. In addition to seeds, the network's main target is to share knowledge and know-how about seed saving among its members and with the wider society too.

Figure 7. Participants experimenting seed saving

Linking seed saving networks and ESSRG work on policy, Borbála Lipka presented current and upcoming seed policies of the EU during an interactive workshop. Borbála, being a member of Magház and working on the Planet4B project at ESSRG, has been following the development of the new seed legislation of the European Union. The presentation and discussion covered the current situation of the seed legislation, the recent updates on the new seed law and the potential consequences of the adoption of the new law on seed saving networks.

A number of international agreements have an indirect impact on how seeds can be accessed and exchanged in the EU, such as the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and its supplementary agreement, the Nagoya Protocol, FAO's International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (ITPGRFA) or the United Nations' Declaration on the Rights of

Peasants And Other People Working In Rural Areas (UNDROP). Directly, the distribution of seeds in the EU is currently regulated by 12 different Directives covering

- variety registration of the seed that is to be marketed,
- production rules of these varieties, and
- labelling and packaging requirements.

As the current seed market is regulated by fragmented policies and the directives are adopted with significant differences by the EU Member states creating controversies, the EC aims to develop a new, common framework to harmonize the seed market and align it with EU strategies, such as the Green Deal, Biodiversity Strategy or the Farm to Fork Strategy.

The proposal for the new legislation was adopted on July 5, 2023 and is currently debated by the European Council. One of the main disputes around the new seed law concerns the transfer of conservation varieties, including rare and endangered varieties. According to the current seed legislation (12 Directives), conservation and amateur varieties can be exchanged without registration and therefore without complying with the so-called DUS standards (seeds need to be distinct, uniform and stable). This exemption from variety registration, according to Borbála, is greatly beneficial for maintaining genetic diversity and supports the work of seed networks both in Hungary and all over the European Union. However, according to the proposal, the scope of conservation activities and actors involved in conservation would be much narrower and even that is under debate that any exchange of such rare and endangered varieties would be considered marketing, thus need to comply with the same bureaucratic and administrative requirements as in the case of the industrial seed marketing. Such a regulation would jeopardise the work of organizations and networks working for the diversity of cultivated plants because it would set unrealistic requirements for small-scale seed growers.

During the discussion, participants shared their experiences from their own countries and discussed how rules should support the smaller actors dedicated to agrobiodiversity too.

4. Summary

During the creator workshop, a diversity of events were offered for participants to better understand policy work related to the food system, including agrobiodiversity, UCs and seed policies; and to immerse in embodied, creative and hands-on experiences. The creator workshop highlighted the diverse values and benefits of UCs, and promoted sustainable agricultural practices preserving UCs via food system research examples, a field visit and a panel discussion. Discussions and networking in a friendly atmosphere allowed participants to share common experiences and challenges related to UC production, processing, marketization and seeds.

During the panel discussion at the DIVINFOOD annual meeting, participants could learn about inspiring good practices on how to include UCs in local food communities, collective catering and urban food policy. The event facilitated new connections and collaborations among the different actors who joined the event, which will lead to additional projects related to UCs.

To conclude, the event has proven that various people from different sectors (including researchers, growers, processors, civil society) share a commitment to preserve and revitalize UCs along the value chain. While UCs still face challenges in the current agri-food system, engaged actors can contribute to the promotion and use of less common species at various levels.

Annex I - Program

Underutilised Crops Week in Budapest

Program and Information Sheet

2 - 5 June 2025

Budapest, Hungary

We invite you to four days of programs dedicated to forgotten and underutilised crops (UCs)! Building on synergies between EU projects and related networks and providing opportunities for networking, we organize a series of activities to bring to light the forgotten values of diverse and resilient but underutilised crops from various aspects.

The program is co-organised by the RADIANT, LegumES and Divinfood projects and the DIVERSICROP network.

The program will include the following:

RADIANT Creator Workshop - 2nd and 3rd June

ESSRG's Food Projects: explore and network

How does ESSRG seek to shape the food system? During this networking event, ESSRG will lay the table and you can learn how we work with local authorities and stakeholders, and how we aim to create an impact on food policies.

Seed Saving at Szezon Kert

UC production starts with the seeds. However, access to seeds of less common species is limited. How can you access UC seeds? How does a community seed bank work? During a field visit at our RADIANT Aurora farm, [Szezon Kert](#), Páty, you can actively participate and gain hands-on experience about horticultural UC seed saving techniques and learn about the network of seed savers from the members of the Hungarian community seed bank, [Magház](#).

Policy convergence roundtable (RADIANT - LegumES - Divinfood)

A key part of our programme, a roundtable discussion with invited speakers will explore how policies can support UCs. The roundtable will converge around creating momentum at the local and European levels for cultivated biodiversity, given that food and agriculture policies at various institutional and sectoral scales may play a pivotal role in stimulating the incorporation of agrobiodiversity in the food system. Notably, minor crops can galvanise the transition to a much-needed dietary diversification. The session is embedded in Divinfood’s annual meeting.

Program Overview

Dates	Program
2nd June	<p>14.00 - 18.00 ESSRG’s Food Projects - explore and network <i>Location: Central European University, Budapest, Nádor street 15</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 14.00 - 15.30 Project presentations and discussion • 15.30 - 16.00 Coffee break • 16.00 - 18.00 HOPEN workshop: We will engage in a playful and interactive format, taking stock of where we are coming from, where we find ourselves now, and what kind of future we desire to create together (and with UCs). <p>18.00 Visit to the exhibition “Traces of Life” at CEU Open Gallery. The exhibition takes part in the OFF Biennale Budapest 2025. <i>“The exhibition Traces of Life interrogates the interdependence of human and non-human life, exploring their intersecting mobilities and rights in hostile environments.”</i></p> <p>19.00 Dinner</p>
3rd June	<p>8.00 - 14.00 Seed Saving at Szezon Kert <i>Location: Páty (joint public transportation will be organized)</i></p> <p>16.00 - 17.30 A policy convergence roundtable co-organised with RADIANT, LegumES, Divinfood</p>

	<p>Location: European Union Information and Cultural Centre in Budapest, Budapest, Lövház street 35</p> <p>18.00 Dinner</p>
4th June	<p>DIVERSCROPS Science & Policy Training School Location: Central European University, Budapest, Nádor street 15</p>
5th June	<p>DIVERSCROPS Science & Policy Training School Location: Central European University, Budapest, Nádor street 15</p>

